

D4.3 | Market Ready Product

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the final market-ready product that was developed under the framework of project CleanAir for provision of an innovative measure to inactivate SARS-CoV-2 viruses and other infectious pathogens in the medical environment. Based on a novel technology, the consortium has successfully developed the PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device to market readiness. The device will be marketed as an air disinfection device for medical facilities in the European market after project finalization and after medical device clearance by the FDA as a medical circulating air cleaner in the US market. The device is produced by Villinger GmbH, who has internally over the timeframe of the project adapted its manufacturing capabilities in order to provide the required infrastructure and quality standards to achieve series production of 30 units per year in the first year after product launch and for 60 units in the second year after market entry.

1 General

Air disinfection devices have become more important than ever. With the Covid-19 pandemic turning into an endemic and the presence of other infectious and dangerous diseases, air disinfection devices are essential in controlling the spread of airborne pathogens in healthcare facilities. Specifically in the medical environment, indoor air quality can have a significant impact on health, particularly for patients with underlying health conditions or weakened immune systems. Furthermore, health practitioners are at a high risk of exposure to airborne pathogens and other pollutants, particularly in high-risk areas such as ICUs and emergency departments. Air disinfection devices can contribute to increase the level of protection for healthcare workers, by reducing the risk of exposure to harmful bioaerosols.

By now, several countries have issued policies that set specific indoor air standards for healthcare facilities, particularly in high-risk areas such as isolation rooms and operating theaters. An air disinfection device can help healthcare facilities to meet these regulations and ensure that they are providing a safe environment for patients and staff.

The PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device has been designed for the purpose of air disinfection in medical facilities, removing dangerous bioaerosols from the air and inactivating them. Therefore, the PIA™ device is intended to be used as an easily installable safety measure for European and North American medical facilities in order to reduce the risk of exposure to harmful bioaerosols, including SARS-CoV-2 aerosols as well as other viruses, bacteria and mold spores.

The device is conceived for continuous operation and constant treatment of the indoor air. One specific advantage of the PIA™ device is by incorporating the LEA™ technology, the air drawn through the device is almost unaffected by the laminar electrode array within the device, meaning that a fairly low noise emission can be safeguarded. The overall noise level in medical rooms must be kept as low as is necessary according to the specific type of room. Guideline values are contained in DIN EN 13 779 "Ventilation of non-residential buildings" and are, for example, max. 45 dBA in medical operating rooms and in corridors, max. 35 dBA in other rooms used for medical purposes, max. 40 dBA in offices.

The consortium was committed to stay below this threshold of 35dBA, in order to provide an air disinfection measure that can be applied to as many rooms as possible in the medical setting. With a maximum noise emission level of 32,4dBA (fan speed 10), PIA™ can be constantly activated even in room settings such as patient rooms, where interference with sleep caused by excessive noise levels has to be mitigated.

2 Technical Specifications

2.1 Technical Data

Parameter	Unit
Product name, type	PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B
Model description	Designed for installation in cassette ceilings remote controlled 10-speed fan settings 3 LEA™ (Laminar Electrode Array) active electrode panels with heated collector electrodes
Air source	Axial Fans
Airflow rates	Fan speed 1 = 85 m ³ /h Fan speed 2 = 161 m ³ /h Fan speed 3 = 236 m ³ /h Fan speed 4 = 312 m ³ /h Fan speed 5 = 387 m ³ /h Fan speed 6 = 463 m ³ /h Fan speed 7 = 539 m ³ /h Fan speed 8 = 614 m ³ /h Fan speed 9 = 690 m ³ /h Fan speed 10 = 765 m ³ /h
Noise emission	Fan speed 1 = 7,6 dBA Fan speed 2 = 10,1 dBA Fan speed 3 = 12,3 dBA Fan speed 4 = 18,2 dBA Fan speed 5 = 22,9 dBA Fan speed 6 = 23,4 dBA Fan speed 7 = 25,2 dBA Fan speed 8 = 28,1 dBA Fan speed 9 = 30,6 dBA Fan speed 10 = 32,4 dBA
Input	220-240 VAC, 50-60 Hz 100-130 VAC, 50-60 Hz
Electrical connection	3 core single phase cable
Dimensions	620 x 620 x 240 mm
Weight	16,8 kg
IP class	IP40
Quality & safety	Manufactured under ISO 9001 Conforms to 2014/35/EU Low Voltage Directive (LVD), 2006/42/EG Machinery Directive, 2014/30/EU Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) Directive, 2011/65/EU Restriction of Hazardous Substances Directive

	CE
High voltage exposure safety features	Security screws prevent access of not qualified persons to the electrode array; Switch that deactivates the device, if the device door is opened when the device is switched on
Fan exposure safety features	No access to fan without opening tools.

2.2 Device elements

Figure 1: Device elements

3 Before Device Usage

3.1 Transport and Storage

The PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device should only be handled and transported within its original packaging in order to prevent unwanted damages to the device and to mitigate scratching of the surface. Only once the device is ready for installation, the customer is advised to remove it from the packaging. When shipped to the customer, the package will contain the following items:

- PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device
- Original remote control (1pc.)

- Original spare pre-filters (2 pcs.)
- Original wire rope (5m)
- Original rope clamps (8pcs.)
- Original snap hooks (4pcs.)

Also for storage, it is recommended to the customer that the PIA™ device is stored within its original packaging, under the following storage conditions:

- Storage in a dry, protected environment.
- Storage conditions: 0°C to 40°C (32° F to 104° F), relative humidity 40-80%, no condensable humidity, atmospheric pressure conditions of 0.95 atm and 1.05 atm.

3.2 Device Installation

Due to the evaluation of the product packaging according to ASTM D4169-22, damage to the device during shipping is relatively unlikely. Nevertheless, once the installation location for the PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device is defined, the customer should conduct a quick visual inspection of the device after unpacking.

Furthermore, before installation it is essential that the customer ensures that the PIA™ ASC-CC9500B device is protected from voltage spikes. It is therefore required that from customer side, a surge protection unit, also referred to as a transient voltage surge suppressor (TVSS) is available and connected to the device directly or that the power network that is used for connection of the device has integrated measures for surge protection.

The following tools are required for installation:

- 6x30mm dowels
- Screw hooks
- Electrical-, or manual screwdriver
- Drilling tool
- Hammer

The installation involves several steps. First, the existing cassette ceiling panel where the PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device shall be installed is to be removed. Four holes with a diameter of 6mm and a depth of approximately 35mm are to be drilled into the concrete ceiling, where the device later will be mounted. 6x30mm dowels will then be secured in the holes. To the dowels, the screw hooks will be applied. Then the snap hooks and the wire rope will be attached to the device as shown in figures 2 – 6.

Figures 2 – 6: Snap hook application steps

Before the device is then hung onto the installed screw hooks, the 3-phase electrical wiring is to be connected as shown in figure 7.

Figure 7: Connection schematic

When the device is connected, it has to be aligned with the opening in the cassette ceiling and hung onto the installed screw hooks.

4 Device Usage

The device is only to be used in enclosed spaces with relative humidity 40-80%, atmospheric pressure conditions of 0.95 atm and 1.05 atm. The device has to be connected to the facility's voltage supply within the installation space between the concrete ceiling and the ceiling cassette panels. It is noted in the user manual that the device should only be operated when correct and secure installation into the cassette ceiling and correct connection to the voltage supply can be safeguarded. Furthermore, it has to be ensured that the device's air inlet and air outlet are free of any objects that may restrict the airflow.

5 Device Maintenance

The only maintenance procedure required for the PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device is the replacement of the device's pre-filters which are required to prevent large particles to enter the LEA™ electrode array of the device. The pre-filters will accumulate dust over time and are therefore to be replaced every 6 months after continuous operation. This can be done by personnel from the medical facility since the procedure is explained in the device's user manual. Before replacing the pre-filters, the device is to be switched off using the remote control and to be disconnected from the power source. The pre-filters are located behind the door of the device which can be opened using one of the two keys that are supplied with the device. The pre-filters can be removed by unlocking the latch, simply pulling the framing of the filters outwards and replacing with a new filter. Once both pre-filters are

changed, ensure that the device door is securely closed before switching the unit back on via the remote control.

Figure 9: Step 1 of the replacement procedure; the device door is to be opened and the used pre-filters to be removed

Figure 10: Step 2 of the replacement procedure; the new pre-filters are to be installed by clipping them into place

Figure 11: Step 3 of the replacement procedure; the device door is then to be shut and the device can be switched on again

The pre-filters are throw-away type air filter units which are to be disposed as follows: Before the user begins with the replacement procedure, a plastic bag is required. The pre-filters are to be removed as described in figure 9. The used pre-filters are to be placed

gently into the plastic bag in such way that the release of dust and particles into the air is prevented. Therefore, the pre-filters should not be shaken. The plastic bag is then shut and to be placed in the waste disposal.

6 Troubleshooting & Device Repair

During the electrical safety testing, it has been investigated that there are specific events that may cause the device switching off, however remaining fully functional. The device simply has then to be switched on again by the user. These events are:

Interference signal

If the device's receiver for the remote control receives a signal from any other source than the original remote control for the device, the device will shut-off.

Loss of input voltage

If the input voltage to the device is interrupted, the device will shut-off.

Electrostatic discharge

If a sudden and momentary flow of high electric current or high frequency to the device occurs, the device will shut-off.

Should damage occur to the device, the customer is advised to contact Villinger, since the repair attempts by the customer are deemed impractical due to the device's and technology's complexity. Villinger's support team will be able to diagnose the issue and assess whether repair in the field is possible or if the device has to be repaired by Villinger in-house or exchanged all together. By ensuring proper customer relations, Villinger in this way ensures that PIA™ can continue to provide safe and effective air disinfection, ensuring a clean and healthy environment for patients, staff, and visitors.

7 Standards compliance

2006/42/EG Richtlinie 2006/42/EG des Europäischen Parlaments und des Rates vom 17. Mai 2006 über Maschinen und zur Änderung der Richtlinie 95/16/EG (Neufassung)

Veröffentlicht in L 157/24 vom 09.06.2006

2014/30/EU Richtlinie 2014/30/EU des Europäischen Parlaments und des Rates vom 26. Februar 2014 zur Harmonisierung der Rechtsvorschriften der Mitgliedstaaten über die elektromagnetische Verträglichkeit (Neufassung)

Veröffentlicht in 2014/L 96/79 vom 29.03.2014

2011/65/EU Richtlinie 2011/65/EU des Europäischen Parlaments und des Rates vom 8. Juni 2011 zur Beschränkung der Verwendung bestimmter gefährlicher Stoffe in Elektro- und Elektronikgeräten

Veröffentlicht in 2011/L 174/88 vom 01.07.2011

2014/35/EU Richtlinie 2014/35/EU des Europäischen Parlaments und des Rates vom 26. Februar 2014 zur

Harmonisierung der Rechtsvorschriften der Mitgliedstaaten über die Bereitstellung elektrischer

8 Device Safety Instructions

In this section an overview is provided about the safety instructions that are given to the customer in the device's user manual.

8.1 Safety information related to the intended use and reasonably foreseeable misuse

The PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device is only designed to inactivate airborne viruses, bacteria and mold spores as well as CFUs. Do not use the PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device in environments that have poisonous gases, fumes, noxious smoke, or other chemical risks.

Do not expose the device to water. Do not use in wet or damp environments. Failure to comply with this instruction may cause damage to the unit and electric shock or other injury to the user.

The PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device is designed to inactivate airborne contaminants that may damage the human respiratory system. However, the use of this system does NOT mean that other safety measures such as dust masks can be ignored. Seek medical attention immediately if you experience any worrying respiratory symptoms.

The PIA™ ASC-CC 9500B device is only to be operated when its door is closed and latched. Operation with the door open is deemed misuse of the device.

8.2 Installation Safety Information

The device should be installed only by qualified persons.

Consult your local building code for approved wiring & installation.

Use the appropriate equipment for the installation on the ceiling.

To reduce the risk of electrical shock, do not expose the device to water or mist.

To prevent serious injury from accidental operation, make sure the power cord is disconnected from the power source and the device is switched to OFF before installation or making any adjustments.

When installed, the bottom of the device must be at least 2,5m (8,2 feet) above the floor surface.

When installed, mounts must be anchored to the building structure which will support a minimum of at least 50kg. Never mount to surfaces such as dry wall or false ceiling grids, etc.

Position the device in such way that it is at least 0,6m (1,9 feet) away from any corner or from any heating, cooling, or air circulation vents.

Secure the ladder when accessing the device for maintenance or installing it.

Secure the installation site so that not qualified persons cannot access the site.

Secure the device and all the instruments for installation so that they do not fall on you and persons involved in the installation.

Never try to stick any tools through the fan inlets or outlets of the device.

8.3 Safety Information Regarding the Use of the Device

Do not handle plug or appliance with wet hands.

Do not damage the power cord.

Do not unplug by pulling on cord. Grasp the plug, not the cord.

Do not use with any opening blocked; keep free of dust, lint, and anything that may reduce airflow.

Do not use if airflow is restricted. If the air paths become blocked, turn the device off and unplug from power source. Remove all obstructions before you plug in and turn on the device again.

Do not use if the device is not working as, it should, or has been dropped, damaged, left outdoors, or came into contact with water.

Do not use the device in the following areas:

- *Wet or damp areas*
- *Outdoor areas*
- *Spaces that are enclosed and may contain explosive or toxic fumes or vapors (lighter fluid, gasoline, kerosene, paint, paint thinners, mothproofing substances, or flammable dust)*

Turn off all controls before unplugging the device.

Never drop or insert any objects into the openings of the device.

The device should only be used in a room with temperatures between 0°C and 40°C (32° F and 104° F), relative humidity 40-80%, atmospheric pressure conditions of 0.95 atm and 1.05 atm.

8.4 Safety Information Regarding Maintenance of the Device

To reduce the risk of injury and electric shock hazards, disconnect the device from the power source before making adjustments, servicing or changing any components of the device.

8.5 Explanation of Graphical Symbols Added to the Label

Symbol	Meaning
	Caution, high voltage
	Date of manufacture
	Manufactured by
	Serial number
	Waste of Electrical and Electronic Equipment; the device must be disposed in recycling bins, take-back programs, collection locations, or on-demand collection services, specifically designed for electronic waste.
	The manufacturer affirms the good's conformity with European health, safety, and environmental protection standards

Figure 12: Device rendering – explosion drawing (minor components such as screws or washers not shown)

Figure 13: Device rendering – device with remote control and user manual

